

THE SPECIFICS OF THE INSPECTION OF THE SCENE AND THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE INVESTIGATIVE ACTIONS THAT NEED TO BE TAKEN

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<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10649835>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th February 2024

Accepted: 11th February 2024

Online: 12th February 2024

KEY WORDS

Investigative action, theft, inspection of the scene, the composition of the crime.

ABSTRACT

The article reveals the role, significance and content in the preliminary investigation of the investigative action on the inspection of the scene by law enforcement officers. In this regard, the investigative actions and related issues that should be undertaken by the investigator, the investigator and the prosecutor during the inspection of the crime scene of theft were analyzed.

The modern period of Uzbekistan's development as an independent state is characterized by many problems, some of which stem from the current criminal situation in the country. Despite the active actions of law enforcement agencies, the rates of certain types of crimes are growing. In recent years, the number of crimes involving property has increased. Theft is one of the most common crimes against property, which is rarely detected. The peculiarity of thefts is their low degree of disclosure. The unsatisfactory results of work on the detection and investigation of thefts, as well as preventive measures, indicate a tendency to significantly reduce the number of persons who committed thefts against the background of an overall increase in crimes recorded by this group. The methodological base of criminology is insufficient for modern conditions, which affects the effectiveness of the work of internal affairs agencies in preventing and detecting theft.

Accordingly, the place and importance of all investigative actions that should be carried out in a criminal case of theft is much more important. Of these, an inspection of the scene is an investigative action – the most important way to obtain information about the theft. During the inspection, it is necessary to inspect not only the house in which the theft was committed, but also other adjacent premises, since it was through these premises that the criminal could enter the scene. It is also necessary to inspect the area around the scene of the incident, as there may also be traces of the criminal's shoes, tread marks left from the wheels of vehicles.

A qualitative check of the scene of the incident allows you to obtain enough information to create versions and assumptions about the identity of the perpetrator, which contributes to his further search and disclosure. For example, the age of the criminal and his social status can be judged by the uniqueness of the stolen items. According to the method of entry into the room, you can determine his physique, height, physical strength or professional skills.

The analysis of the situation of secret theft of other people's property allows you to identify the intentions of the criminal (which arose suddenly, committed in advance), the

duration of preparation for the crime, etc. The installation of stolen items allows you to assess the places where you can sell the property and criminal connections of the suspect, as well as draw a conclusion about the professional skills and interests of the criminal.

The inspection of the scene should be continued, starting from the threshold of the object where the offender entered the dwelling, that is, where the door, wall or ceiling was damaged, window panes were removed. It is in these places that you are more likely to find a gun to break into a door or wall, footprints, handprints, and cigarette butts. When examining the premises, you should pay attention to the places where the criminal took a valuable object-things, as well as objects that his hand can touch (door handles, moved objects, open boxes, emptied bottles), since it is on these objects that you can find traces of hands, feet, shoes, micro-objects. When detecting traces of compression, bumps, scratches, pay attention to their size and distinctive sides. They are photographed and taken away to find a weapon to break into. It is important to determine whether fragments or tips of burglar weapons remain at the scene, as they will be used to find (identify) burglar weapons. When detecting cases of penetration into a dwelling dug out of the ground, it is necessary to look for traces of tools (shovels, picks) that left these traces, since in the future, looking at them, it will be possible to identify the weapon used as a weapon of crime. On soft soil in this place, you can find footprints, shoes of the criminal. In this situation, it is necessary to take soil samples, because later, when the suspect is caught, soil particles left over from the theft site may be found in his shoes. They use them as evidence when conducting an appropriate examination. In some cases, the suspect takes the stolen items not where they entered, but in another place (for example, by entering the house through a wall or window and locking the door from the inside). Therefore, in order to trace the further path of the criminal, find his tracks and use the search dog, it is necessary to find out where he came from and where he took the stolen items. There are also cases when, during manual or automobile transportation of stolen property from one place to another, as a result of a container malfunction or careless handling of the packaging (box), the substance inside the container can spill out onto the road and leave a trace on it. The detection of such traces allows you to trace from the scene of the incident to the criminal's house or the place where the stolen items are hidden. After carrying out this investigative action and initiating a criminal case, it is advisable to interrogate the victim, witnesses, identify the suspect, detain and search his house, inspect the suspect's clothes and things seized from him, give evidence, identify the suspect, conduct an experiment, interrogate the suspect (accused).

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